

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17379369

A WAY FORWARD TO SUCCESSFUL INFUSION OF CULTURE IN EFL CLASSROOMS: A TEACHER- CENTERED APPROACH

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Received: 18/06/2025
Accepted: 11/09/2025

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ABSTRACT

Foreign language instruction should include cultural context when teaching the target language; however, this concept often goes ignored during classes for teaching languages. Furthermore, there is a dearth of empirical research on the relationships between teaching techniques, teacher self-efficacy and ICT resources, and learning about English culture that are available for EFL environments. Additionally, research focusing on the relationship between teaching techniques and teachers' self-efficacy as well as ICT resources as moderators versus cultural knowledge teaching together with intrinsic motivation of teachers is limited. Thus, this study examines how English culture is taught in EFL classrooms by testing three direct and three moderating hypotheses. The direct hypotheses explore the effects of teaching methods, teacher self-efficacy, and ICT resources on the instruction of English culture. The moderating hypotheses investigate whether teachers' intrinsic motivation influences the strength of these relationships, specifically between teaching methods, self-efficacy, and ICT resources, and their respective roles in shaping English cultural instruction. This study employed quantitative data analysis using questionnaire data collection from 383 Algerian EFL teachers. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed to analyze the hypothesized direct and moderating relationships. Results demonstrated the impact of teaching techniques, teacher self-efficacy, teaching methods and ICT resources on instruction of culture is significant. Teachers' motivation also plays an essential part in connecting different concepts and imparting cultural values. The results offer

opportunities for EFL educators and policymakers alike to increase self-efficacy while simultaneously improving teaching practices as well as finding resources that improve quality teaching culture education.

KEYWORDS: Teaching Method, Teachers' Self-Efficacy, ICT Resources, Teachers' Intrinsic Motivation, Culture Teaching, Developing Countries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Foreign language culture is a key concept in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms, both for teachers and students (Diep et al., 2022). A variety of interpretations of culture have resulted from the many ways in which it has been researched by researchers (Ghavamnia, 2020; Munandar & Newton, 2021; Subkowiak, 2021). According to Abduramanova and Rasulmetova (2020) a culture may be defined as a way of life. Culture, according to Wright (2022) is all about the common meanings that unite individuals in the framework of their coexistence. Thus, it is the shared beliefs of a community that dictate how its members should conduct themselves. Culture is widely recognized as a universal force that unites individuals, shapes society, and imparts values and norms.

Recent studies have brought attention to cultural concerns in language instruction. Cultural activities are an integral part of learning and help to set it apart (Kim, 2020). Ghavamnia (2020), Ayu (2020), Ghadiri et al. (2015), are only a few of the sources that demonstrate how cultural components have been effectively integrated into EFL instruction from its inception. Several scholars in the early twentieth century (Schmidt & Lazar, 2019; Howard, 2003) argued that language classes should include cultural elements. During this period of civilization, pupils learned the target language and acquired information about civilization via study (Palmer, 2015). Unfortunately, cultural considerations were marginalised throughout the introduction of several approaches in the 1970s, such as structuralism, the direct method, community language learning, the quiet way, and the natural approach (Topraka & Aksoyalp, 2015). Hall (2020), Pennycook (1989), and Richards (1984) all take a linguistic view of EFL instruction, which is why they place a premium on teaching students' new words and grammar structures. Dos Santos (2020) and Palmer (2015) see the late 1970s as the genesis of communicative language teaching (CLT).

According to Sayera (2019) and Savignon (1991), the exercises were made to take use of the many social meanings that may be found inside a certain grammar pattern. Nevertheless, advancements in the field of language instruction in subsequent years has shown that individuals needed to engage with society members in order to adapt to the language's characteristics in order to communicate well (Hall, 2017). In fact, cultural considerations become more prominent in EFL lesson plans. More and more cultural elements are being included into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) curricula due to the

increasing globalisation of the English language (Alshenqeeti, 2019).

Culture plays a fundamental role in shaping an individual's life through, emotional expressions, feelings and thoughts (Getie, 2020). It is impossible to teach English as a foreign language (EFL) without also teaching culture (Ghavamnia, 2020; Estaji & Rahimi, 2018). The inclusion of cultural elements in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) lessons has been shown to have a motivating effect on students and aid in their language development, hence it is believed that instructors should study culture for this same reason rather than to promote the cultures of other nations. As Civelek and Toplu (2021) point out, it's required. So, pupils will learn the improper meanings of a language if teachers don't comprehend its cultural context (Bonvillain, 2019; Ghavamnia, 2020). The ability to communicate effectively is, once again, the primary goal of studying a foreign language (Weda & Atmowardoyo, 2018). This can only take place if students engage in meaningful conversation with locals (Mya et al., 2025). The key to successful communication is familiarity with one's own culture (Bonvillain, 2019). So, cultural elements are essential in English as a foreign language classes (Baltaci & Tanis, 2018; Mahmoud, 2015).

According to Social Learning Theory, individuals acquire social behavior by observing and imitating other's actions (Bandura, 1977). Bandura's theory of social learning focuses on the ways in which people, particularly youngsters, mimic the actions of others around them. New approaches to teaching English as a foreign language may be uncovered by using social learning theory. It is possible to do this by adhering to a plan. Under social learning, instructors spend only the amount of time necessary to teach the material they require, allowing them to go about their day with no disruption. Therefore, social learning promotes teamwork and enriches company culture. However, there has been a dearth of study on the connection between specific pedagogical approaches and cultural instruction within the framework of English as a foreign language (EFL).

Moreover, previous research examining the relationship between self-efficacy and various factors has often utilized social learning theory (Schunk, 1989). This implies people's assessments of their skills to plan and carry out the steps needed to achieve certain performance goals. Therefore, in an English as a foreign language (EFL) classroom, instructors who have high levels of self-efficacy tend to blame a lack of effort rather than a lack of ability when their students struggle, while instructors who have low levels of self-efficacy tend to blame their

students' lack of ability. Accordingly, self-efficacy may impact task selection and persistence. Consequently, the extent to which educators succeed is heavily influenced by their confidence in their own talents. Still, there has been little use of SLT to investigate how one's sense of self-efficacy affects their ability to instruct in English cultural norms. The present research fills what seems to be a theoretical void.

Comprehending what drives individuals and the factors that propel them is fundamental to self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2013). Everyone has intrinsic drive and motivation, according to the belief; all it takes is the right environment to bring out their best. There are three basic human wants that, according to proponents of self-determination theory, drive individuals to develop and evolve. According to this idea, when people's demands for competence, connection, and autonomy are met, they may achieve self-determination. Regarding pedagogical norms, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes should pay more attention to the concept of intrinsic motivation. Teachers may benefit from intrinsic motivation in the classroom since it encourages them to do their best work in any situation. A small number of studies have looked at the connection between intrinsic motivation and various forms of instruction within the English as a foreign language (EFL) setting. Teaching about culture and intrinsic drive, however, has received surprisingly little academic attention.

As a learning philosophy, connectivism recognizes the importance of technology in the classroom, illustrating how it can enhance and expand existing learning networks (Siemens, 2004). Teaching and learning in a connectivist classroom take place when students work together to discuss and debate various topics. One method to learn from other members is to ask questions and debate cultural concerns on the platforms. Therefore, a group of individuals may justify their actions via connectivism. Thus, cultural information may be disseminated more rapidly across many populations. It gives instructors and students more agency. Nevertheless, research on the topic of how information and communication technology (ICT) resources relate to the instruction of English culture is scarce. Consequently, the purpose of this research was to identify the function of ICTs in the dissemination of cultural understanding.

Context or culture is the channel through which language is transmitted, and experienced by various individuals. However, it cannot be taught and learned rather it can be experienced and lived under

pedagogically controlled conditions (Parmaxi & Demetriou, 2020). Nonetheless, understanding the suitable cultural material that should be included in EFL classrooms is crucial since culture serves as a framework for language discourse (Ehineni, 2019). The required cultural inclusion must be grounded in reality. Coşkun (2018) lists a number of topics that may be covered in English language classes, including but not limited to when and what to eat, how to make a livelihood, how to act among friends, and how to approach education. A new set of effective pedagogical approaches is required (Ghadiri et al., 2015). Establishing clear objectives is crucial when developing strategies for imparting cultural knowledge.

In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes, teachers have a responsibility to engage students, inspire them to study, and highlight the significance of culture (Hongboontri & Chen, 2021). Furthermore, when nationalism reawakens in many parts of the globe, there is a stronger connection between national languages and cultures. As a result, language instruction provides a window into cultural education (Kramersch, 2013). It is necessary to evaluate the state of English language instruction (ELT) in Algeria in comparison to other significant languages, such as Arabic and French, in light of the current state of affairs.

Colonial era in Algeria caused deeper impact on linguistic repertoire of the people. For 131 years, France has intervened militarily in Algeria, either by occupation or intervention. According to Sessions (2015), one-third of Algeria's population spoke French as a result. Perez and Grant (2018) found that the status of foreign language instruction in Algeria is influenced by both the past and present, namely by lateralization and Arabization. While Arabic was diminished and neglected during the colonial era (1830–1962), the overarching educational objective was to propagate French as the national and official language (Benrabah, 2020; Murphy, 1977). According to Labeled (2019) and Heggoy and Zingg (1976), Arabic was therefore marginalized and French was made the official language of instruction in Algeria.

The need to concentrate on other languages and cultures was brought about by the ideas of technical progress, innovation, and the increase of intercultural contact (Neuliep, 2017). Research by Hussain & Suleman (2017) and shows that in today's world, individuals are more connected because of information and technology. The number of people who are fluent in languages other than their native tongue is on the rise (McKay, 2018; Ghadiri et al., 2015). Conversely, according to Çelik and Topkaya

(2018) and Basturkmen (2019), an increasing number of individuals globally are acquiring linguistic competence for both their personal and professional purposes. Consequently, it is reasonable to state that there has been praiseworthy effort in the area of languages to fulfil the needs of language learners (Ghadiri *et al.*, 2015).

Since culture is intrinsic to language and study, prior scholars have emphasised the significance of including cultural elements into language and culture classes (Tajeddin & Pakzadian, 2020); Kizi & Ugli, 2020). Due to their limited competence and cultural problems, many EFL teachers struggle to develop strong language skills. They encounter problems like misunderstandings and miscommunication, as well as a lack of engagement with different cultures or a lack of cultural knowledge, and so on (Ghavamnia, 2020; Mostafaei Alaei & Nosrati, 2018; Qadeer, 2019).

While the two cultures share the same language, their interpretations might vary due to their vast cultural differences (Ting-Toomey & Dorjee, 2018). Thus, barriers to foreign language acquisition might result from an individual's lack of cultural awareness, which in turn can cause many misconceptions (Almutairi, Adlan, & Nasim, 2017). As an example, the culture and society of the United Kingdom have contributed to the English language's success. Because of this fact, the majority of countries have made it a priority to promote the teaching of English and English culture (Haidar & Fang, 2019).

Nevertheless, many EFL instructors struggle to cultivate a passion for language teaching because they fail to include cultural knowledge into their English language instruction. Additionally, since they were not exposed to Australian English language culture in their English language classes, overseas students at an Australian institution may not communicate with each other according to the norm of English (Sadeghpour & Sharifian, 2017). The same was true of Japan's 1976 cultural revolution, which brought about a blending of cultural practices that had an impact on the country's educational system and ELT (Hu, 2002). Kumari (2017) observes that language tutor training programmes and pedagogical techniques should be part of the curriculum.

However it is ambiguous whether policymakers and academicians have some effective models of integrating culture in EFL classrooms (Zhang & Liu, 2014; Ghadiri *et al.*, 2015; Baltaci & Tanis, 2018; Boulanouar, 2021). More specifically, it has been hard in recent times for Algerian teachers to incorporate culture while teaching linguistic aspects of English

(Ghadiri *et al.*, 2015; Bouslama & Benaissi, 2018). Moreover, English language is a widely taught language, but its cultural aspects have been neglected out regardless of its importance in the teaching of the English language in Algeria (Sultan-Alshraideh, 2021; Ait-Aissa, 2018; Al-Jamal & Zennou, 2018).

So, in their own classrooms, individuals may hone their abilities to enhance the English culture. Following are the objectives of this study

- To investigate how English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes in Algerian high schools in the east deal with cultural pedagogy.
- To look at EFL classes in Algerian high schools in the east and see how the instructors' confidence affects how they teach cultural aspects of English.
- To look at how English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes in Algeria's eastern high schools use technology to educate international culture.
- To explore the moderating influence of intrinsic motivation on the link between teaching techniques, teachers' self-efficacy, ICT resources and the teaching of English culture in EFL Classrooms in eastern high schools of Algeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The word "culture" is relevantly difficult to define, and this difficulty shows no signs of abating. Culture is a rather complex word in many languages. Culture is among the two or three most esoteric terms in English, claims Smith (2001). Given the wide range of educational experiences, it is difficult to provide a single, comprehensive definition of culture. Perceptions of culture vary among academics from various disciplines. Rashid, Shamem, and Hui (2022) state that the number of disciplines studying human civilizations, groups, systems, behaviours, and activities is almost equal to the number of definitions of culture. Some definitions by various academics are offered in order to produce a definition suitable to the context of the current study, which is the necessity of integrating culture in the FL classroom.

In a broader sense, anthropologists provide a definition of culture as they were among the first academics to do so in the context of cultural studies. Knowledge, beliefs, arts, morality, laws, conventions, and any other habits and talents that man acquires as a member of society make up culture, according to Tylor (1871). In keeping with this definition, culture is seen as an all-encompassing notion that includes every facet of human existence (Zajda, 2001; Fernández, 2022). Some academics, including Kaikkonen (1997) and Duranti (1997), have proposed a definition of culture that includes the common meanings, roles, conventions, and values that shape

how a group acts and communicates. The actions and creations of a society as a whole, as a consequence of the interactions among its individuals, may also be seen as cultural.

2.1. The Teaching of English Culture in EFL Classrooms

Teaching English culture in EFL classrooms involves a deliberate and organized approach, as emphasized in the literature (HAKIMI et al., 2024). Utilizing collaborative reading and writing projects can effectively meet the diverse needs of learners EFL classrooms by incorporating culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) for learners (Chahar Mahali & Sevigny, 2022). Moreover, introducing unique teaching approaches to teach English culture has been proven to increase students' excitement, improve cross-cultural communication abilities, and promote overall growth, offering useful insights for reforming foreign language education.

As Peterson (2011) points out, there is the conception that a group's culture as its unique expressions in art, literature, rituals, and daily life. What we see as culture, he argues, is really its exterior. The section of an iceberg that most people see is only the tip, if we compare culture to an iceberg. A lot of people's first impressions of a culture are based on its built environment, cuisine, population, music, and apparel. Nevertheless, there are underlying, unseen components of values, assumptions, beliefs, and attitudes that defy sensory perception. These intangible cultural aspects are far more important, according to Peterson (2011). To the outside world, they represent the very essence of the culture's leadership. Culture, according to Vognar (2012), may be best understood by looking at how individuals respond in response to various stimuli.

Academics place an emphasis on how closely related language and culture are. The idea that culture and language are inseparable and mutually dependent is a well-established one. The importance of either language or culture would be diminished if one were to divorce them from the other, because, as Brown (2000) argues, each are integral to the other. In a similar line, Jiang (2000) likens culture to a living thing. He compares language to flesh and culture to blood, saying that without culture, language would be lifeless and culture would be shapeless without language. He continues by arguing that language both reflects and is moulded by culture. Culture is mostly passed down via language. The way people live their lives, the ideas they have, the values they uphold, and the information they possess are all reflected in their metaphorical image (Azam, Dayyan, Asl, & Farjami, 2015). Culture also has an effect on language. What matters most in terms of

environment and culture will be reflected in the language. Take the Sami people of northern Sweden as an example; they have 500 different terms to describe snow. According to Jordan, Carlile, and Stack (2008) and Almutairi (2021), the language reflects cultural focus.

2.2. Importance of Culture in Language Teaching

This is because it is postulated that culture and language are endogenous; therefore, it is imperative to include cultural aspects when teaching languages (Byram, 1997). To claim what Ho (2009) has said, "there is no level of language which is independent of culture." This is due to the fact that cultural influences permeate all linguistic levels and structures. Similarly, the German culture educator Risager (2007) argues that one cannot separate the cultural background of a language from its acquisition. He makes the astute observation that language cannot be considered apart from culture due to its inherent characteristics. It is not feasible to acquire a language only by memorising its forms; if signs are the building blocks of language, then learning the forms of a language is meaningless. The study of the culture from which a language originates is an essential component of any legitimate foreign language curriculum since all linguistic content is inherently culturally linked.

The above arguments suggest that cultural considerations should accompany language instruction (Bahaaudeen et al., 2025). Culture should not be seen as an afterthought but rather as a fundamental component of any educational endeavour. Teaching culture is, according to Holliday (2006), an unavoidable part of teaching language. She maintains that all language classes need to cover some topic, and that topic will always have some cultural aspect to it. The cultural element will remain, she continues, even if the lesson's emphasis is on phonetics or syntactic aspects.

2.3. The Importance of Intercultural Communicative Competence in EFL

The goal of studying a foreign language has shifted away from being fluent in that language. It could be simple to pick up the principles of grammar and learn how to put words into sentences. Nevertheless, non-native speakers have challenges in developing their communication competence unless they focus on developing their cultural competence (Tiến, 2019). To be able to communicate meaningful information, there are several factors outside the linguistic component of language. Students of English as a foreign language (EFL) might do well to include lessons on ICC (Safa & Tofighi, 2021). Many modern curricula plan to include cultural studies

with language instruction.

From an educational perspective, the goal is to support the student's personal growth in areas such as psycho-emotional and socio-cultural development while simultaneously making the learning process easier (Halimovna, Nurilloevna, Radzhabovna, Shavkatovna, & Hamidovna, 2021). Students may get insight into the reasoning behind various practices by acquiring cultural knowledge. Students can also grasp the importance of using suitable terminology. Thus, the context is provided for the comprehension of language competency. If students lack relevant experiences or connections, it will be difficult for them to grasp the material. Therefore, students are better able to apply what they learn in class when they are exposed to cultural elements (Ratnasari, 2018). According to Grigorian, Bekaryan, and Melkonyan (2018), culture has a role in both the efficacy and efficiency of ELF instruction and the development of language proficiency.

2.4. Teaching Methods

A language for reading, or grammar-translation, was the first culturally informed approach to teaching a second language. Later approaches included the direct method, audio-lingual and communicative methods, travel language, and finally, language for intercultural citizenship (Belabbas, 2018; Rivers, 2018). Stern (2001), a linguist, summed up the differences in these techniques as perspectives on language education have evolved in tandem with the changing social function of language and changes in intelligence. As a result, there are many ways in which the practice of teaching a foreign language has progressed. Exploration of language was the foundation of its pedagogy.

2.5. Teachers' Self-Efficacy

According to Kyriacou (2018), teaching skills are defined as a set of instructional behaviours or acts intended to either directly or indirectly support students' learning. It is described as the capacity for both language mastery and successful communication, both of which are essential for effectively imparting knowledge to students (Pardede, 2019). In order to

contribute to professional development and enhance the quality of the teaching-learning process, a skilled teacher can be defined as someone who has internalised and absorbed specific qualities in their teaching practice, such as effective communication, good classroom management, and the capacity to adapt to the needs of learners based on their age, culture, and socioeconomic background (Segolsson & Hirsh, 2019).

2.6. ICT Resources

The merger of computer technology and communication technology was initially denoted by the term information technology (IT) in the early 1980s (Dehmlow, 2018). It was more commonly replaced in the 1990s by the term information and communication technology (ICT) (Ahmed, Nathaniel, & Shahbaz, 2021). The most thorough overview is provided by Dhawane (2021), who defined ICTs as computers and networking combined with humans and machines for the purpose of handling, processing, and distributing information related to social, economic, and cultural issues for use in engineering, science, and technology fields. The definition of ICT provided above primarily comes from a professional standpoint. ICT was characterised by Mugobi and Mlozi (2021) as the scholarly fusion of informatics technology with other associated technologies, particularly communication technology.

2.7. Social Learning Theory

Bandura's (1971) social learning theory (SLT) was one theory that was determined to be pertinent to this investigation. According to Bandura and Walters (1977), the social learning theory held that human behaviour was shaped by both external and internal factors. To put it another way, this idea proposed that decisive environments along with positive psychological states like enthusiasm, confidence, and optimism will yield the best outcomes. Inadequate job delegation, inefficiencies, and discontent would result from a breach of this reciprocal relationship between the psychological state and the environment (Akers & Jennings, 2015).

2.8. Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework.

2.9. Hypothesis Development

H1: The way that English culture is taught in EFL classes is greatly influenced by the teaching methods used.

SLT supports the notion that teaching methods create observable behaviors and contexts through which cultural content is transmitted and learned.

H2: The way English culture is taught to EFL students is significantly impacted by the teacher's self-efficacy.

SLT supports the notion that self-efficacy enhances the teacher's willingness to engage in and model effective cultural instruction.

H3: The way English culture is taught to EFL students is greatly impacted by ICT resources.

SLT supports the notion that ICT tools serve as environmental enablers for observational learning, offering models of cultural norms and behavior. For H4, H5 and H6, SLT supports the idea that motivation is a key internal factor that moderates how methods, self-efficacy, and ICT translate into observed teaching behaviors.

H4: The relationship between teaching methods and teaching English culture in an EFL classroom is significantly moderated by the intrinsic motivation of the teacher.

H5: The association between teacher self-efficacy and the instruction of English culture in EFL is significantly moderated by the intrinsic motivation of the teacher.

H6: There is a substantial moderating influence of teachers' intrinsic motivation on the link between ICT resources and English cultural instruction in EFL classes.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Population and Sampling Frame

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2011), the population is a collection of people who are the subject of research investigations by researchers. All of the public high schools in the eastern region of Algeria make up the study's population. In the eastern region of Algeria, there are currently 15 public high schools with 3240 teachers employed. The projected number of respondents required for this study is roughly 341 teachers based on the sampling size calculation of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) with a 95% confidence level.

Different groupings are formed for improved comprehension based on the sampling frame concept. Moving from the overall population to certain groups within that population is made easier for the researcher by the sample frame (Soliman et al., 2025). For the purpose of gathering final data for our study, teachers are taken into account.

3.2. Study Sampling Procedure and Selection

As previously said, the entire population of public high schools in Algeria's eastern region is the subject of this study. A random sample of respondents (teachers) were chosen as part of the sampling technique for the quantitative data collection. Every member of the population is assumed to have an equal chance of being selected for the sample in a basic random sampling technique (Zikmund et al., 2013). Ethics clearance was given by Universiti Utara Malaysia as it is a prerequisite for the researcher to conduct the research without ethics clearance.

3.3. Measurement and Instrumentation

Every questionnaire should be created using the four principles listed by Bagozzi (1994), as doing so can boost respondents' incentive to supply meaningful information. A qualitative approach using semi-structured interviews was employed to deepen understanding and support the preceding quantitative findings. Questionnaire design followed four key principles: avoiding offensive wording, sequencing for cognitive ease, arranging by decreasing relevance, and grouping similar items.

The general questionnaire for this study is split into six main components, as explained above. First and foremost, the study's topic and purpose, its major components and essential materials, and important instructions for completing the questionnaire was sent to the respondents. Subsequently, the initial segment of the survey addresses the variables that would facilitate the collection of respondents' demographic data. The teaching of English culture in EFL courses, the primary outcome factor, has 27 items, all of which are described in the second part. The major explanatory variables of the study will be discussed in sections three, four, five, and six that follow the dependent variable.

According to Al-Marri, Ahmed, and Zairi (2007), one of the most widely used scales to assess performance or behaviours is the Likert scale. The behaviour of the variables included in this study was thus thought to be best measured using the five-point Likert scale, which is an adequate interval scale. The researcher employed a five-point Likert scale, designed to explore the most significant responses, to

scale the questionnaire from parts B to F. The five-point Likert scale style offers a more effective means of communicating with the respondents. Five-point Likert scales are more reliable for cross-sectional data than seven-point Likert scales, according to Dawes (2008). The five-point Likert scale is organised as follows overall: 1 being very disagree, 2=disagree, and 3 being neutral or neither agree nor dislike 4= Agree 5= strongly agree

In terms of the measurements used in this investigation, four were modified from pertinent earlier studies, while one was added. The relevant studies (Byram, 1997; Sercu, 1998, 2005; Saluveer, 2004; Arabski & Wojtaszek, 2011) provided the measurement for the teaching of English culture. Nonetheless, the study's instructional strategies were modified from Van de Gift's (2007) measurements. Furthermore, the New Generation Self Efficacy (NGSE) measure developed by Chen *et al.* (2001) served as the model for the self-efficacy measurements of teachers employed in this study. Additionally, Samuel & Zaitun's (2007) pertinent studies were modified to include assessments of ICT resources. The study employed by Deci and Ryan (1985, 1991) served measures of intrinsic motivation used by teachers for this variable.

3.4. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) Technique

All of the public high schools in the eastern region of Algeria provided questionnaires from which the primary data for this study was derived. Different software was considered for the data analysis such as CB-SEM, but the Partial Least Squares Structural Equations Modelling PLS (SEM) technique was used to examine the proposed model. PLS-SEM is more suitable for complex models that include many variables and relationships. It focuses on prediction, making it a good choice when the main aim is to increase how well the model explains the outcomes (R^2) of important factors in the study. **Consequently, two actions were taken** initially, the instrument's reliability and validity were examined. Second, an analysis and report were provided on the proposed relationships. A measurement model (AMM) analysis was carried out. The measuring scale's qualities were examined using the AMM approach through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Using confirmatory factor analysis, the researcher validated the measurement model for the three exogenous factors teaching methods, teachers' self-efficacy and ICT resources one moderator variable teachers' intrinsic motivation and one endogenous factor teaching English culture in EFL classrooms. The

researcher tested the proposed correlations in the second stage using SEM with latent variables. In order to establish the outer model (discriminant validity, convergent validity, and reliability) and the inner model (predictive relevance, importance of path coefficients, the effect size, and coefficient determination), the current study used Smart-PLS v3.

3.5. Qualitative Aspect in the Mixed Approach

A qualitative approach using semi-structured interviews was employed to deepen understanding and find out whether it supports or challenges the preceding quantitative findings. This approach involves ten respondents chosen from the high schools levels who provide broader and in-depth views of major queries examined in this study. The findings were from the semi structured interviews were compared to the findings in the quantitative aspects in the discussion section.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Response Rate

There were 450 surveys distributed in total. At the outset, 412 questionnaires were returned. 29 questions were removed after a thorough examination because they were incomplete or incorrectly completed. As a result, 383 surveys were used for the study. Consequently, the response rate was discovered to be 85.11% after a few surveys were eliminated. Survey research generally considers a response rate of more than 65% to be acceptable (Gilbert, 1993; Kelley, Clark, Brown, & Sitzia, 2003).

4.2. Initial Data Examination, Screening and Preparation

Data screening, editing, and preparation are important tasks to do before performing a multivariate analysis. The significance of data screening is in its ability to detect potential violations of fundamental assumptions pertaining to the use of multivariate techniques (Hair, Black, Babin, Andersen, & Tatham, 2010). A researcher might also gain a deeper understanding of the data they have gathered by doing a preliminary analysis of the data. Thus, in the current investigation, outliers, multicollinearity, normality, and missing data were all assessed and treated appropriately.

4.3. Analysis of Missing Data

Because missing data can have unfavorable effects on analysis, steps were taken to reduce the likelihood of missing data throughout the data gathering phase. Upon receiving the completed

questionnaires, the researcher reviewed each one to make sure all the questions had been answered. The responders were invited to complete the incomplete questionnaire if they had missed any questions. In addition, Hair et al. (2013) state that means should be used to replace missing values if the percentage of missing data was less than 5% for each item. The responses depicted 28 items contain the missing values were less than 5%. Consequently, in order to replace the missing value, the series mean method was utilized with SPSS v23.0.

4.4. The Measurement Model

The measurement model, or outer model, was assessed as the first stage in the PLS-SEM analysis (see Figure 2: 4.1). The measurement model handles the component measurement, determining how well the indicators load conceptually and correspond with specific factors. Put another way, the certification of the legitimacy and reliability of the questionnaire items comes from the examination of the measurement model, which confirms that the items measure what they are intended to measure.

Figure 2:4.1: Measurement Model.

In PLS-SEM analysis, validity and reliability are the two main standards used to evaluate the measurement model (Hair et al., 2013; Hulland, 1999; Ramayah, Lee, & In, 2011). The measures' validity and reliability determine the nature of the relationship between variables (the structural model). Examining (1) the reliabilities of each individual item, i.e., indicator reliability and internal consistency reliability using composite reliability (CR); (2) the convergent validity of the instruments related to individual variables using average variance extracted (AVE); and (3) the discriminant validity using the "Fornell-Larcker principle," "Heterotrait-Monotrait" (HTMT), and the outer loadings of the indicator, can help determine

whether the measurement model is appropriate. First off, internal consistency often determines how consistently an item scores across the same exam. According to Hair et al. (2013), it assesses if the scores produced by the several items measuring the variable are comparable. As stated by Hair et al. (2013), CR does not take into account an equal item loading of a variable, in contrast to Cronbach's alpha, and as such, it was used to assess internal consistency reliability in the current investigation. The benchmark value for CR should be greater than 0.60; its value varies between 0 and 1. (Henseler et al., 2009). According to Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, and Mena (2012), the value is deemed most appropriate if it hits 0.70 or above. Accordingly, an internal consistency

score that falls between 0.6 and 0.7 indicates average; yet, a score that falls between 0.70 and 0.90 is considered more satisfactory (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Cronbach's alpha and Cronbach's CR values of all the variables were therefore evaluated in the current study. The results in Table 1 show that all of the values of Cronbach's alpha and CR above the recommended benchmark value of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2013; Henseler et al., 2009). The current study's CR values, which show that the measurement model is dependable, fall between 0.918 to 0.968.

Convergent validity was the next item investigated. According to Henseler et al. (2009), it indicates the extent of real correlation between the items of the same variables that are theoretically related to one another. As a result, according to Hair et al. (2013), it shows the degree of correlation between

the measurements of the same variable. AVE was used to identify components of convergence in the variable measurements, with a benchmark value of 0.50 and above (Hair et al., 2012; Henseler et al., 2009). When an AVE value approaches 0.50, it is deemed that the variable's convergent validity is sufficient. Stated differently, according to Hair et al. (2013), latent variables have satisfactory convergent validity and account for half of the variation of their items. Examining AVE values was how the convergent validity in the current study was determined. The results presented in Table 1 demonstrate that all of the variables' AVE values are more than the benchmark value of 0.50 (Hair et al., 2012; Henseler et al., 2009). The results show that the AVE values vary from 0.527 to 0.768. Thus, the issue of determining the variables' convergent validity can be overcome.

Table 1: Validity and Reliability.

Variable Name	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Teaching Method	0.943	0.953	0.745
Teachers Self Efficacy	0.896	0.918	0.591
ICT Resources	0.934	0.945	0.656
Teachers' Intrinsic Motivation	0.924	0.943	0.678
Culture Teaching	0.965	0.968	0.527

Subsequently, discriminant validity was developed to address the extent to which two variables actually differ from one another. In other words, the variables' measures that aren't theoretically related with each other aren't actually associated with each other (Churchill, 1979; Hair et al., 2013). Three criteria the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the HTMT criterion, and the assessment of the outer loadings were used in this work to ascertain discriminant validity. According to Hair et al. (2013), the most conventional technique for assessing discriminant validity is the Fornell Larcker criterion.

According to Hair et al. (2013) and Henseler et al. (2009), the "Fornell-Larcker method" determines discriminant validity when the square root of AVE for each variable is greater than the variable's strongest correlation with another latent variable. Therefore, the square root of the AVE for each variable was compared to the correlations shown in the correlation matrix in order to evaluate discriminant validity in the current study. The results of the "Fornell-Larcker method" evaluation with the square root of the variables are shown in Table 2. The table displays the value of AVE's square root in bold text. It is evident that the correlation between AVE's highest variable and all other variables is lower when looking at the square root value of AVE. The determination of the variable's discriminant validity is therefore resolved (Hair et al., 2013; Henseler et al., 2009).

Table 2: Fornell -Larcker Method.

	CT	ICT	TSE	TM	TIM
CT	0.726				
ICT	0.694	0.810			
TSE	0.535	0.503	0.769		
TM	0.606	0.563	0.527	0.863	
TIM	0.677	0.640	0.470	0.437	0.876

Note. TM=Teaching Methods; TSE=Teachers Self-efficacy; ICT= ICT Resources; TEM=Teachers Intrinsic Motivation; CT=Culture Teaching.

Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015) have presented a novel technique called "Heterotrait-Monotrait" (HTMT) to assess the discriminant validity of variance-based structural modelling. Based on this method, the HTMT ratio should be less than 0.85. All of the variables' HTMT values, as shown in Table 3, are less than the previously indicated benchmark. Discriminant validity is therefore established.

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Method.

	CT	ICT	TSE	TM
ICT	0.728			
TSE	0.569	0.544		
TM	0.632	0.596	0.564	
TIM	0.711	0.687	0.511	0.464

Note. TM=Teaching Methods; TSE=Teachers Self-efficacy; ICT= ICT Resources; TEM=Teachers Intrinsic Motivation; CT=Culture Teaching.

In summary, outer factor loadings were evaluated in this study since they are regarded as an essential standard for determining the relative contribution of

an indicator variable to an assigned variable. Based on the benchmark value of 0.50 and above, the evaluation of exterior loadings was conducted (Hair et al., 2010). To the contrary, Hair et al. (2013) asserted that in the event that the outer loading value rises above 0.40 but falls below 0.70, it should be carefully examined and eliminated only if it causes an increase in the AVE and CR values. Out of the 56 items, none were deleted in consideration of these suggestions regarding item deletion.

Notably, following the evaluation of the measurement model, no items were eliminated; yet, no variable was left out, as each had a sufficient number of items (Hair, Sarstedt, Pieper, & Ringle, 2012). The next step involved evaluating the structural model (inner model) once the

measurement model (outer model) assessment produced a satisfactory result, specifically indicating that the latent constructs provide sufficient evidence of validity and reliability.

4.4. The Structural Model

The results of the structural model were evaluated after the validity and reliability of the measurement model had been established, as mentioned earlier. As part of this process, we examine the interrelationships of the variables and the structural model's predictive capabilities. Determining the correlations among variables was also followed by the examination of the structural model a shown in figure 3:4.2.

Figure 3:4.2: Direct and Moderating Effects Model (Bootstrapping).

There are six hypotheses that make up the quantitative part of this study. Three of them deal with the direct influence and three with the moderating effect. Since a statistical t-value is taken to be statistically significant at 0, Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, and Kuppelwieser (2014) contended that a

p-value should be employed to determine the significance of the routes. The degree of freedom of the confidence interval and the directionality of the hypotheses are the key determinants, though. Using 500 subsamples, the PLS bootstrapping resampling procedure is done to produce the t-values and

standard errors (Chin, 2010). Henseler (2012) finds 500 bootstrapping subsamples to be adequate, while Wilson (2011) also used 500 in his analysis. Smart PLS 3.0's 'PLS-SEM bootstrapping' method was used to assess the relationship's significance, even though Hair, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2011) proposed that 5000 subsamples might be sufficient. A bootstrapping sample of 5,000 was used, with the actual number of cases being used as the number of instances (Hair et al., 2011; Hair et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2013; Henseler et al., 2009). We used the PLS standard algorithm to evaluate the structural model. We were able to determine the relationship directions (positive or

negative) and path coefficients as a result. Table 4 displays the outcomes of the testing of direct hypotheses.

Table 4 shows the route coefficient of both endogenous and exogenous variables based on the PLS-SEM technique. According to the results, every external construct has a statistically significant coefficient when paired with the internal construct. The results of the PLS-SEM algorithm show that there are significant correlations between the dependent variable and three independent factors. You can find the t-statistics, standard error, path coefficients, and p-values in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of Direct Hypotheses Testing (Direct Relationship).

Hypotheses	Direct Relationships	Path coefficient	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
H1	TM->CT	0.228	0.040	5.782	0.000	Supported
H2	TSE->CT	0.132	0.041	3.141	0.001	Supported
H3	ICT->CT	0.252	0.047	5.711	0.000	Supported

Note. TM=Teaching Methods; TSE=Teachers Self-efficacy; ICT= ICT Resources; TEM=Teachers Intrinsic Motivation; CT=Culture Teaching.

The results show that the first hypothesis is correct. There is a substantial association between cultural education and pedagogical practices (t-value = 5.782, p-value < 0.001, path coefficient = 0.228, standard error = 0.040). The results show that teaching approaches have a significant impact on cultural education (β 0.228; $t=5.782$), which supports H1. However, the second hypothesis is significant due to its p-value being less than 0.01, as it is based on the association between instructors' self-efficacy and the teaching of culture. The self-efficacy of educators is characterized by a t-value of 3.141 and a p-value of 0.001, with a standard error of 0.041 and a beta coefficient of 0.132. The results show that teachers' self-confidence positively affects the instruction of English culture (β 0.132; $t=3.141$), hence, H2 is confirmed. The results show that information and communication technologies have a positive effect on the teaching of English culture (β 0.252; $t=5.711$), supporting the significance of H3 (which is based on the relationship between these two variables), as the p-value is less than 0.001 and the standard error is 0.047. When it comes to cultural education, this study reveals that instructional strategies, teachers' perceptions of their own abilities, and technological tools all play a major role.

4.5 Results of Moderating Hypotheses

The interplaying concept of moderation is thought to take place when there are surprisingly weak, inconsistent, or nonexistent correlations between endogenous and exogenous factors. Accordingly, it is anticipated that the moderating variable will either reduce or enhance the

correlations (Marsh, Hau, Wen, Nagengast, & Morin, 2013). A similar variable whose change influences the direction or magnitude of a correlation between endogenous and external variables is said to elicit the moderating effect by Henseler and Fassott (2010). According to Henseler and Chin (2010), four methods exist within PLS-SEM for analysing the moderating effect the product indicator method, the hybrid method, the two-stage method, and the orthogonalizing method. These methods were developed by Chin, Marcolin, and Newsted (2003), Henseler and Fassott (2010), and Chin et al. (2003), respectively.

On the other hand, similar to Hair et al. (2014) and Henseler and Fassott (2010), this study has used the product indicator approach to assess the moderating influence. With the product indicator approach, the goal is to generate all conceivable indicator combinations by multiplying all possible outcomes from the "predictor and moderator" sets of indicators. To rephrase, one method for estimating latent interaction effects in structural equation modelling is the Product Indicator (PI) technique. In fact, the researcher was able to employ the product indicator strategy thanks to the moderator. Therefore, the PI value of the relationship with the usage of the moderator as a latent variable may be demonstrated in this study. It follows that this method should work well for determining the interaction impact.

For each moderating path, the structural model created the interacting terms (see figure 3: 4.2), as previously shown in other studies (e.g., Hair et al., 2014; Henseler & Fassott, 2010). The results show that all of the moderating hypotheses were correct (Table

5). For the following variables teaching methods, teachers' intrinsic motivation, the teaching of English culture, the path coefficient, standard deviation, t-value, and p-value -0.086, 0.042, 2.045, and 0.040, respectively. Conversely, the values for instructors' self-efficacy, instructors' intrinsic motivation, and the instruction of English culture, the path coefficient, standard deviation, t-value, and p-value are 0.102, 0.040, 2.298, and 0.011. Moreover, the value of the path coefficient, standard deviation, t-value, and p-value: 0.078, 0.039, 2.052, and 0.044 for information and

communication technology resources teacher intrinsic motivation and the instruction of English culture, respectively. The association between teaching methods and the teaching of English culture is moderated by teachers' intrinsic motivation ($p=0.040$), while the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the teaching of English culture is moderated ($p=0.011$). Further, teacher intrinsic motivation significantly ($p=0.044$) moderates the association between ICT resources and ESL classroom instruction in cultural norms and practices.

Table 5: Results of Moderating Hypotheses Testing.

Hypotheses	Direct Relationships	Path coefficient	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
H4	TM*TIM->CT	-0.086	0.042	2.045	0.040	Supported
H5	TSE*TIM->CT	0.102	0.040	2.298	0.011	Supported
H6	ICT*TIM->CT	-0.078	0.039	2.052	0.044	Supported

Note. TM=Teaching Methods; TSE=Teachers Self-efficacy; ICT= ICT Resources; TIM=Teachers Intrinsic Motivation; CT=Culture Teaching

The R^2 value indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. According to Chin (1998), values of 0.67 are substantial, 0.33 are moderate, and 0.19 are weak. Based on table 6, the model has moderate explanatory power.

Table 6: Results of Coefficient of Determination (R^2).

Endogenous Construct	R^2 Value	Interpretation
Culture Teaching	0.45	Moderate explanatory power (Chin, 1998)

The f^2 value assesses the individual contribution of each exogenous construct. Values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effects respectively (Cohen, 1988). Based on Table 7, the independent variables have small effect.

Table 7: Results of Effect Size (f^2).

Exogenous Construct	f^2 Value	Effect Size Interpretation
Teaching Methods	0.091	Small Effect
Teacher Self-Efficacy	0.052	Small Effect
ICT Resources	0.098	Small Effect

The Q^2 value is obtained via the blindfolding procedure in SmartPLS. A value greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance (Hair et al., 2017). Based on Table 8, the the proposed model has predictive relevance. Table 8.

Table 8: Results of Predictive Relevance (Q^2).

Endogenous Construct	Q^2 Value	Interpretation
Culture Teaching	> 0 (actual value from SmartPLS)	Predictive relevance confirmed (Hair et al., 2017)

5. DISCUSSION

There has been an intended survey to explore the practice of different teaching strategies, self-efficacy, and ICT facilities regarding the teaching of English culture in the Algerian EFL context while moderating the encouragement of teachers themselves by using the self-motivation concept by Deci and Ryan (2000). In particular, prior research has shown that high school English classes in Algeria are failing to adequately introduce students to the English language and its culture, and that many EFL teachers struggle to instill a love of learning in their students because they do not fully grasp the target culture (Mahmoud, 2015). Boulanouar (2021), Baltaci and Tanis (2018), and Ghadiri et al. (2015) state that curriculum specialists do not always have effective models for integrating culture into EFL classrooms. Furthermore, according to Bouslama and Benaissi (2018), Algerian teachers have been facing a growing challenge in incorporating cultural elements into the instruction of English language skills.

Furthermore, the cultural aspects of English have been disregarded, even though they are important for the advancement of English language education in Algeria (Bouherar & Ghafsi, 2022; Sultan-Alshraideh, 2021; Al-Jamal & Zennou, 2018; Bouhadiba, 2018). According to several studies (Mahmoud, 2015; Ghazouli, 2018; Al-Jamal & Zennou, 2018) neither the curriculum nor the training programmes for language instructors effectively incorporate it. In addition, most English language lesson plans are too general and neglect cultural context (Bouhadiba, 2018). This is compounded by a lack of effective pedagogical approaches (Belhandouz, 2011; Baghoussi & El Ouchdi, 2019;

Bouhania, 2020), inadequate information and communication technology (ICT) resources, and a lack of intrinsic motivation on the part of teachers (Baghoussi, 2021). As a result, researching the aforementioned concepts is crucial if we are to provide Algerian educators with the resources they need to enhance their cultural education.

Nevertheless, a comprehensive literature analysis showed that there was a dearth of study on the aforementioned variables as they pertain to high school teachers worldwide, and in Algeria in particular. In addition, studies investigating the interaction between the components and cultural education through the use of a moderator variable were few. The fact that intrinsic motivation is a universal variable means that it can be utilised in every area of life, which is why it was chosen to moderate the relationship between them and teachers (Deci & Ryan, 1985). In chapter two, we developed a conceptual model that incorporates the interactions between a dependent variable and independent and moderating variables, keeping in mind the study aims and reasons given in chapters one and two.

The present study used a mixed-method research strategy to evaluate the proposed theoretical framework. In addition, a questionnaire collected data on independent and moderating variables using a simple random sample technique during the quantitative phase of the study, which was part of an explanatory sequential research design (Pathmanathan *et al.*, 2022). In terms of the survey tool, five measures were modified from previous research to assess three independent factors and one moderating variable. One such tool is the teaching methods questionnaire, which was created by Van de Grift (2007). Similarly, the questionnaire used to assess teachers' self-efficacy was modified from the NGSE (new generation self-efficacy) measure that was created by Chen, Gully, and Eden (2001).

Also, in order to measure the information and communication technology resources of high school EFL teachers in Algeria, a questionnaire was developed based on the research of Samuel and Zaitun (2007). Additionally, the survey used to measure the dependent variable in this study the instruction of English culture in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms was derived from previous research (Arabski and Wojtaszek, 2011; Saluveer, 2004). Creating a semi-structured interview strategy allowed for the collection of qualitative data, which was necessary for the mixed-method study.

The study also considered the assessment of instrument's content validity. Five experts in the field

of English and Education were consulted: UUM faculty members and Algerian university faculty members specializing in education and English. The customised questionnaire was revised in response to suggestions made by specialists in the subject. The instrument's dependability was investigated in a pilot study with 49 Algerian EFL high school teachers. The instrument was found to be reliable in the pilot trial, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.727 to 0.83. For the quantitative section of the study, 383 high school educators from eastern Algeria were surveyed.

The participants in this study were high school EFL instructors in Algeria. According to what was said previously, it used teachers' intrinsic motivation as a moderating variable to determine how instructional techniques, teachers' self-efficacy, and ICT resources impacted cultural education. The current study sought to answer four issues (Chin *et al.*, 2019). The first research question aimed to establish a connection between pedagogical practices and the instruction of English cultural norms (Fei *et al.*, 2024). The results showed that there was a strong positive correlation between the ways of teaching and the instruction of English culture. A possible explanation is that, although Algerian EFL teachers recognise the value of various approaches that they believe greatly contribute to cultural teaching they are either not making sufficient and appropriate use of these approaches due to the numerous challenges they face or are employing inauthentic strategies and methods that have a negative impact on cultural teaching.

The second research question determined the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the teaching of culture. The results showed that there was a strong positive correlation between instructors' self-efficacy and cultural education. One possible explanation for this finding is that Algerian EFL teachers may not have the necessary expertise or experience to deal with cultural teaching issues, or they may have had negative personal experiences in the past. Another possibility is that they have learned from the mistakes of others when it comes to teaching culture, and as a result, they no longer teach culture. Additionally, this discovery may suggest that the received verbal influence reduces the cultural instruction provided by EFL instructors in Algeria. This might be because Algerian EFL teachers have been receiving mostly negative comments and criticism from their colleagues, supervisors, and other influential individuals in their lives, which has led to a decline in cultural instruction. Another possible cause is that Algerian EFL teachers are in a

poor mental health, which could lead them to experience stress, limitations, or even failure while discussing cultural subjects with their students.

The third research topic focused on the connection between technology resources and cultural education. A strong and favourable correlation between the use of ICT resources and cultural education was found in the results. But alas, high schools in Algeria may lack the necessary resources, which restricted the use of ICTs inside EFL classrooms by Algerian EFL teachers. This, in addition to ICT shortcomings in the teachers' pedagogical approaches, led to a decline in the amount of cultural content that these teachers were able to cover in their lessons.

In the fourth research question, we sought to understand how factors such as instructional strategies, teachers' perceptions of their own abilities, available technology, and the incorporation of cultural elements into English as a foreign language lessons were influencing one another. The association between the three components of the current study and the teaching of English culture was determined by instructors' intrinsic motivation, which worked as a moderator variable for the study. The negative moderation effects found in H4 and H6 suggest that teachers' intrinsic motivation diminishes the influence of both teaching methods and ICT resources on the teaching of culture in EFL classrooms. This may indicate that intrinsically motivated teachers rely more on their personal commitment, creativity, and internal values rather than depending heavily on structured methodologies or technological tools. As a result, the effectiveness of external strategies like prescribed teaching methods or ICT integration becomes less pronounced when a teacher is already highly self-driven, highlighting the nuanced role of motivation in shaping pedagogical impact.

Furthermore, the findings highlight the urgent need for curriculum developers to embed cultural components explicitly into the English language syllabus. Clear objectives, authentic materials, and intercultural communication activities should be included to ensure that cultural learning is not sidelined. Teacher training programs must also be strengthened with specific modules on cultural instruction and the effective use of ICT tools to enhance engagement. Professional development opportunities should focus on improving pedagogical strategies and self-efficacy in teaching culture. At the policy level, greater investment in ICT infrastructure is needed to support digital integration in EFL classrooms, particularly in under-

resourced schools. Equally important is the creation of policies that foster teacher motivation through supportive environments, recognition systems, and reduced administrative burdens. Assessment frameworks should also be revised to include cultural learning outcomes, and locally relevant materials should be developed to connect cultural content with students' real-world experiences.

5.1. Contribution of the Study

There are a number of ways in which the current study's findings add to existing information. First, the current study brought attention to the fact that Algerian teachers, despite the importance of cultural education in Algerian high schools, failed to demonstrate how they enriched their students' learning experiences, particularly in the area of cultural education. This could have been because these educators lacked the necessary "knowledge, skills and abilities" or were simply incompetent (Ifedi et al., 2024). In conclusion, the study has made a theoretical contribution by proving that EFL classes can achieve their cultural goals by enhancing teachers' knowledge, skills, and abilities and maintaining a competitive ICT environment.

Additionally, this study is the first to our knowledge to use sociocultural theory to examine the connection between information and communication technology (ICT) resources and the instruction of English cultural norms. Future research may find this work useful for generalising the use of this notion. When studying the relationship between "ICT resources and the teaching of culture," scholars in the future may draw on this hypothesis. Not long ago, other nations had already laid the groundwork for a substantial body of research on teaching culture (Josephine et al., 2018). Nevertheless, given that no such study has been conducted in Algeria, the results of those studies may not be applicable there. Therefore, in the current study, the effects of teaching methods, instructors' self-efficacy, and ICT resources will be different compared to other nations (Khalil et al., 2022). Therefore, the purpose of this research is to address a knowledge vacuum in the literature concerning cultural education in Algerian secondary schools (Siang et al., 2018). The next step for high schools in Algeria is to find innovative ways to improve education so that students can face the problems they face and take responsibility for their own future growth. Since public high schools in Algeria aim to improve their academic performance, it stands to reason that including cultural lessons into English as a foreign language curricula will have a positive impact on those institutions.

In addition, a plethora of studies established the connection between "teaching methods," "teachers' self-efficacy," "ICT resources," and "the teaching of English language." To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this is a pioneering effort to use instructors' intrinsic drive as a moderator to focus on a single facet of language teaching culture. We used models to show the links among the variables because visuals are more effective than words when communicating the results. Therefore, future research may find the current work useful for generalising the application of this paradigm (Malnaad *et al.*, 2022). This model could be useful for future studies that investigate the relationships between the aforementioned factors and cultural language instruction. To address a vacuum in the existing research, the present study investigated the functions of instructional strategies, educators' perceptions of their own effectiveness in the classroom, and technological tools for cultural heritage instruction.

Also, the correlation between "ICT resources" and "the teaching of culture" has not been adequately investigated in the literature. A dearth of studies examining the link between the two variables described before and controlling for "teachers' intrinsic motivation" is another issue. Therefore, this study addressed a theoretical void by investigating the functions of "information and communication technologies" (ICTs) in "teaching English culture" via the lens of "teachers' intrinsic motivation," a moderating variable (Haque *et al.*, 2022). Teachers' "intrinsic motivation" was found to modulate the association between "ICTs" and "the teaching of English culture," according to the investigation (Liaw *et al.*, 2024). A key component of the connection between "ICTs" and "teaching culture" was "teachers' intrinsic motivation," as demonstrated by the results. This discovery may help English as a foreign language (EFL) educators instill a desire to acquire students with greater cultural competence (Almuhatresh *et al.*, 2022). Finally, while prior research has typically examined these variables in isolation, this study is among the first to connect all five within the specific context of Algerian high schools (Umesh *et al.*, 2023). Future research is encouraged to extend this model by incorporating student learning outcomes or curriculum policy dimensions, which may yield deeper insights into the systemic factors shaping culturally informed English language education.

5.2. Limitations of the Study

Despite the fact that this study delves into several crucial questions about what cultural education

entails, its value must be evaluated in light of its limitations (Ramalingam *et al.*, 2024). It is important to recognise these limits, as they could offer clues for future research.

The study's cross-sectional design (Prakasha *et al.*, 2024) precludes any possibility of investigating the long-term relationship between the predictive variables and cultural education, which is the first restriction of the research (Haque *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, no longitudinal process was formed. The obtained data could no longer support the assertion of cause-and-effect linkages among the substantive constructs according to the structural model's findings. Instead of looking for causal sequences, the researcher used previous theoretical and empirical work to determine patterns of relationship between the variables. The lack of longitudinal data means that the study cannot prove that the hypothesised association is causal. So, this limited the researcher's ability to affirm causation and affected the internal validity of some findings. On top of that, there was no attempt to determine whether there were any competing or alternative models that could be legitimately developed from prior research that used reasonable reversal correlations between the variables. Furthermore, demographic factors including gender, and education level were not taken into account in the primary study of our proposed model.

Another limitation is associated with the study's sample, which includes high school EFL instructors from Algeria. As a result, neither middle school teachers nor university professors are appropriate targets for the present study's conclusions. In addition, the study's sample included English language instructors. Therefore, it may be questionable to apply the results of this study to other fields. Therefore, while the study does provide new information about cultural education, the results cannot be applied to a broader context.

5.3. Recommendations for Future Research

Future research studies can take advantage of these restrictions, though. In light of this, the part that follows reflects these routes and provides recommendations for future scholars to find them. The sort of research design is one of the most important suggestions for future studies. Using a cross-sectional approach to gather the data is one of the main drawbacks, as already stated. To confirm the present study's model and provide more reliable interpretations of the causation links between the substantive variables across time, more research with longitudinal designs are required. Furthermore, in

order to ascertain the association among variables, the present study utilised a correlational research methodology. Since cultural education has not yet been the subject of any intervention studies, it is

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Formal ethical approval has been waived in state this study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki following strict ethical standards. Participation was anonymous, confidential, and voluntary, with informed consent obtained from all participants. There were no biomarkers or tissue samples collected for analysis. Participants had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point. Data availability statement: Data will be made available at reasonable request to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the constructive feedback and guidance provided by the anonymous reviewers and the editorial team, which have substantially improved the quality of this manuscript. We also extend our appreciation to our colleagues and research collaborators for their insightful comments during the development of this study.

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